

*Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid*

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1. Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and overview of the progress

1.1 Objectives

The world agrees that something needs to be done about global warming and climate change. The United Nations Climate Change Conference ([COP21](#)) adopted the first-ever universal, legally binding global climate agreement in order to avoid dangerous climate change. The Paris agreement recognised the importance of averting, minimising and addressing losses and damages associated with the adverse effects of climate change. In 2014, the European Commission presented a [Framework](#) for climate change and energy policies for the period of 2020 to 2030 where ambitious targets envisaged a reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and an increased share of renewable energy.

The introduction and integration of variable renewables and distributed energy generation into the power grid has occurred rapidly over the last decade and will continue to increase in the future. According to [Global Smart Grid Federation](#), however, a higher share of renewables requires a greater ability to maintain balance between power generation and demand on the grid, even in the face of diminishing dispatchable resources. An increasing number of new, small-scale players, such as prosumers and batteries, must be integrated into a system that is turning out to be much more complex as a result of the intermittent behaviour of the renewable resources. Flexible management of energy demand and storage in the distribution grid can greatly increase grid reliability. A combination of renewables and demand flexibility using batteries will become cost-competitive over the next few years as detailed by the [International Renewable Energy Agency](#). The cost-competitive schemes will be supported by ICT technologies in areas such as optimisation and creation of intelligent demand response through integrated ICT components.

Electric vehicles (EVs) are emerging as an integral part of the transport sector and present a secondary market for energy storage and flexibility in the distribution grid. According to the [International Energy Agency](#), European countries are global leaders in EV sales, and among the very top are consortium members Norway and the Netherlands. As a matter of fact, at the moment, an effective and efficient integration of the transport sector with the smart grid is possible only in these countries as only they have a critical EV mass.

The recent surge in interest for local community-based micro markets trading both energy and flexibility emphasises the role of energy storage, distributed renewable production and EVs in such markets and has the potential to disrupt existing business models. A heterogeneous distribution of ownership and operation of energy resources in the distribution grid will create a complex business ecosystem that has not yet been probed in detail. A cross cutting approach for developing innovative business models that takes into account the value created by energy storage and flexibility, regulatory and policy issues along with social factors need to be considered.

In order to explore the potential of the resources mentioned above, to gain traction in the market place and to become a commercial reality, critical barriers must be overcome. There is uncertainty around and a lack of: 1) Grid codes and regulations regarding energy storage in the distribution grid, 2) Integrated flexibility management for energy supply, demand and storage, 3) Novel and supportive ICT solutions for flexibility management, based on recent trends and opportunities related to the Internet of Energy Things, Big data analytics, and visualisation techniques, 4) Models predicting battery (including EV batteries) value and lifetime when servicing the grid, 5) Innovative business models that support an increasing number of smart grid actors such as actively participating consumers, prosumers and other directly engaged stakeholders. The proposed INVADE project addresses the above-mentioned challenges and takes into account future market opportunities to contribute to the European Commission and COP21 targets on a larger scale.

The overall objective of the project is:

INVADE project aims to deliver a Cloud-based flexibility management system integrated with EVs and batteries empowering energy storage at mobile, distributed and centralised levels to increase the share of renewables in the smart grid.

The overall objective is to be reached by the achievement of the following sub-objectives (SOs) and the different achievements obtained in the different work packages (WPs). The work carried out during the reporting period towards the achievement of each objective is also explained:

- SO-1. **Design a flexibility management system** using batteries that supports the distribution grid and electricity market while coping with grid limitations, uncertainty and variability with high penetration of renewable energy, electric vehicles and an increased number of diverse smart grid actors.

Progress:

The flexibility management algorithm is developed and tested in the integrated INVADE platform. The objective of the algorithm is to minimise prosumer cost by optimally using batteries together with the prosumer services including ToU optimization, kWmax control and Self-balancing. Since the INVADE pilots demonstrate certain use case(s) of these flexibility services, their roles, resources, interrelations and constraints are/will be included in flexibility management algorithm.

In order to cope with the underlying uncertainty and variability in predicted inputs, a combination of rolling and receding horizon approach has been adopted. This approach allows us to update input parameters and to react to variation from the nominal or expected conditions.

- SO-2. **Develop a model for batteries including EVs** focusing on prediction of batteries lifetime and impact factors contributing to life extension, and prepare a model for optimal sizing, positioning and scheduling of batteries in the distribution grid.

Progress:

A generic battery model including simplified efficiency characteristics and a generic battery lifetime model including degradation stress factors were developed based on the available information from battery manufacturers and scientific literature. In order to account for the factorization of an arbitrary duty cycle into full cycles at different cycle depths, a rainflow counting algorithm was adopted. Furthermore, the battery lifetime model and the rainflow algorithm formed the basis for a computationally efficient model calculating the marginal cost of degradation in the flexibility management algorithm. With these models, the expected lifetime of a battery in a specified application can be predicted, and the use of batteries is controlled and optimized in a way that high efficiency and extended lifetime can be achieved in normal use conditions, but more detrimental use such as deep cycles is allowed in cases where higher benefits are available.

- SO-3. **Deliver the Integrated INVADE Platform** based on Flexibility Cloud enabling flexible management algorithms, functions and monitoring and control dashboards using Internet of Energy Things, Big data analytics and visualisation techniques to provide real-time information and control tools to stakeholders applying data protection and cyber security principles by design.

Progress:

The first version of the Integrated INVADE platform was tested in a FAT (Factory Acceptance Test) at the end of M18 and officially delivered as part of D8.3. On an overall level, the platform consists of a set of main processes, and the processes and the link between them, constitutes the Integrated INVADE platform.

An API, to be used by pilots, has also been implemented. The API has been designed to receive the asset and time series information, which is necessary for the Flexibility Operator (FO) to operate the pilot sites.

- SO-4. **Integrate the INVADE platform with existing infrastructure and systems in selected pilot sites** in Bulgaria, Germany, Spain, Norway and the Netherlands and validate the platform through mobile, distributed, centralised and hybrid use cases in large scale demonstrations in accordance with national and European regulations and standards.

Progress:

All distributed energy resources (DERs) are being connected, measured and controlled by the INVADE platform. All integrations are based on standard products and open protocols, to avoid customizations that could occur hindrances for future upgrading and new integrations. Its high

importunateness to accommodate easy integrations with other systems, and to be ready for “scaling up” without any “redesign” or manually processes. At M18 the platform started to receive signals from the pilots. These signals will vary due to the need for measuring and controlling devices and the needs of making valuable/accurate predictions. In the Norwegian and the Dutch pilot we will need to integrate with an existing operating platform helping in establishing the requirements for further deployments of the INVADE model where it has to be used in combination with ancillary systems.

- SO-5. **Design innovative and competitive business models** and verify them through planned activities such as analysis of users practises and behaviour, deferral of grid investments, exploitation user group and dedicated workshops to enable monetary and social benefits for a full chain of stakeholders.

Progress:

Digitalisation sparks rapid changes in business modelling globally, in particular the platform/ecosystem based business models, and the energy business is no exemption. In order to create a mutual relationship between this central endeavor of WP9 and the pilots in WP10, the process was speeded up somewhat in order for the business work to have significant impact. A State of the art review (D9.1) was followed by relevant regulatory input on charging and storage from the 5 pilot countries in D9.3, while D9.2 contained analysis on user behavior and technology domestication.

- SO-6. **Engage with full chain stakeholders** to support large scale deployment of INVADE within EEA and beyond and to build awareness of the project and its contribution to both climate change and energy efficiency targets.

Progress:

The project has, through WP3, managed to engage a number of stakeholders in accordance with a new methodology based on Michael Porter’s industrial and cluster analysis. It constitutes our basis for strategic business development based on project’ results. In this context pertinent stakeholder types have been identified and enterprises and organisations representing these invited into the project at different levels and for dedicated purposes.

- On the top level we have organized the Explotation User Group with dedicated representatives from London Transport, DnV-GL, Stavanger municipality. These are proactive in shaping the INVADE ideas and help to open doors too.
- We have and are organising events where targeted stakeholders are actively engaged. Examples of such are ENTSO-E, regulators like NVE, exchanges like NordPool, venture companies like Open Utility etc. Here we are combining knowledge harvest with dissemination. We maintain regular contact.
- We have and still are developing novel business cases for the different pilot owners based on the INVADE platform and business models

developed. That will enable lasting commercial impact and upscale possibilities that can boost earnings and reduce risk.

- Finally, we have started to seek a group of external stakeholders that are willing to pioneer the use of INVADE. This includes Inspiria Science Center, co-owned by the municipality of Sarpsborg in Norway and Malling Property’s (a partner of Saville) parking house for electric vehicles near Sola Airport in Stavanger.

1.2 Explanation of the work carried per WP

The project is implemented in 11 WPs:

WP1	Project Management
WP2	Dissemination and Communication
WP3	Exploitation
WP4	Overall INVADE architecture
WP5	Flexibility Management System
WP6	Energy Storage Technologies
WP7	Communication Platform
WP8	Integrated INVADE Platform
WP9	Business models and energy market structures
WP10	Pilots
WP11	Ethics requirements

Table 1: Work Packages list

The work packages are interrelated in the following ways:

Figure 1: Work Packages flow chart

In addition, there is an interdependency between work packages via the inputs and outputs of the tasks:

Figure 2: Work Packages interdependencies chart

1.2.1 Work Package 1: Project management

Overall objectives of the work package

The overall objective of WP1 is to perform overall project management, including financial management as well as quality, control and communication management of the whole project and their procedures.

These activities cover the following main objectives:

- Implementing procedures for quality, control and communication management within the Consortium,
- Ensuring that the project objectives are reached, milestones achieved and deliverables presented within the given project lifetime and that contractual duties linked to the Grant Agreement signed with the European Commission are respected,
- Managing the financial contribution and distributing it to the Consortium,
- Manage a communication flow between beneficiaries and the European Commission by setting up a communication infrastructure and defining a clear

- and efficient communication flow between its bodies and relations between them,
- and
- Handling the Intellectual Property Rights .

Overall progress at work package level

For the purpose of WP1, the work has been structured according to the following 4 tasks:

- T1.1 Quality control and risks management
- T1.2 Administrative and financial management
- T1.3 Project communication, meetings and reviews
- T1.4 Technical coordination

	WP and Task leaders	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3			
		Q1 (M1-3)	Q2 (M4-6)	Q3 (M7-9)	Q4 (M10-12)	Q1 (M13-15)	Q2 (M16-18)	Q3 (M19-21)	Q4 (M22-24)	Q1 (M25-27)	Q2 (M28-30)	Q3 (M31-33)	Q4 (M34-36)
WP1 PROJECT MANAGEMENT	SMARTIO												
1.1 QUALITY CONTROL AND RISKS MANAGEMENT	SmartIO	★											
1.2 ADMINISTRATIVE AND FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT	SmartIO					★							
1.3 PROJECT COMMUNICATION, MEETINGS AND REVIEWS	SmartIO							★					★
1.4 TECHNICAL COORDINATION	SmartIO												★

Figure 3: Work Package 1 planning

The progress of each individual tasks is elaborated in the following sections.

- T1.1 Quality control and risks management

After generating the deliverable D1.1 Project management that includes the Quality Management and the Risks Management and Contingency Plan, these plans were executed all along the period

Regarding the quality plan, the quality process established to guarantee that the work and deliverables reach the expected quality have been executed regularly, following the steps indicated below:

Figure 4: Quality Management process overview and responsible actors

This process was applied to all the deliverables submitted.

Regarding the risks management, the Project Coordinator generated a Risk log file at the beginning of the project, as indicated in the deliverable D1.1. This Risk log is reviewed regularly, at least during the TCC meetings held every month. Situation of each

risk is analysed, amended when necessary, and new risk may be proposed and added o the list with the affirmative votes of the TCC members. During period 1 nine (9) unexpected risks were added to the Risk log file, but no major risk has materialised so far.

- T1.2 Administrative and financial management

For the administrative and financial management follow-up and day-to-day work, a Project Secretariat (PS) was created, as defined in the DoA. This PS managed all the issues related to the Grant Agreement, the Consortium Agreement, the pre-financing transfers, the quarterly Personnel and Other Costs reporting, the administrative and financial progress report, etc. and request-control all contributions from the partners.

The PS is informing regularly the Project Coordinator and the TCC members of the on-going issues.

- T1.3 Project communication, meetings and reviews

Deliverable D1.2 includes the communication rules for the partners during the project. The communication within the consortium is being perfomed mainly by the PS, but the WP1 leader/Project Coordinator spent also long time dealing with many different issues with the Consortium. The whole communication with the EC is also part of his functions.

During period 1, WP1 managed the agendas, invitations, organisations and the control of all the project’s meetings, as per the following meetings held schedule:

INVADE Physical meetings	2017												2018					
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6
	Year 1												Year 2					
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
Consortium meetings		N							B									B
Technical meetings		N	S						B								N	N
PCC meetings		N																
Workshops			N			B			B	N								
Project events									B						N		G	
EU review															F		G	

Held in Norway, Germany, The Netherlands, Finland, Spain, Bulgaria
 N G TN F S B

Figure 5: Meeting held during period 1

WP1 used a lot of resources in the preparation of the progress report for period 1, generating part of the content needed and controlling and managing the collection of the information from all the partners and from the WP leaders.

- T1.4 Technical coordination

Despite all the technical issues are managed within the coresponding work packages, some technical and scientific coordination is to be executed at a higher level when the

interest and interaction between different WPs open up some technical doubts or disagreements. As an example, this task was in charge of managing everything related to the shift of partners, in Germany, for the execution of the German pilot, assuring that the requirement and commitments stated in the DoA are fulfilled correctly.

Deviations and impact on the task planning

n.a.

Proposed deviations corrective actions

n.a.

Role of Partners

In this WP, while SmartIO assumes the main workload of the 4 tasks, all partners are contributing with personnel and resources for the different reporting and requests of information, attending the consortium meetings, the technical meetings and workshops. The PS is assumed entirely by SmartIO and the administrative and financial personnel of the partners are involved in task T1.2.

1.2.2 Work package 2: Communication and Dissemination

Overall objectives of the work package

The main purpose of the WP 2 Communication and Dissemination (**C&D**) is to organize all activities related to explain, expose and discuss around the INVADE project.

INVADE is an Innovation Action project and that means that all results and developments need to be close to the market. Therefore, we have to attract stakeholders that could get value from INVADE achievements like DSOs for managing distribution grids, retail & aggregator companies that could use INVADE software to operate in wholesale markets, and others. Additionally, we have to engage regulator authorities to ensure that INVADE proposals are going to be legal in the current power systems or at least we have to produce recommendations for upgrading the current regulation. All potential stakeholders to be considered in the C&D strategy and plan will be analysed in WP2 and WP3.

Overall progress at work package level

The work carried out in WP2 in period 1 has been focused to meet the objectives specified in the DoA. It has been structured according to the following planned 5 tasks:

- T2.1 Dissemination and communication

- T2.2 Digital media
- T2.3 Technical Advisory Group (TAG)
- T2.4 Participation in EC events and project clusters
- T2.5 INVADE large scale events

	WP and Task leaders	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3			
		Q1 (M1-3)	Q2 (M4-6)	Q3 (M7-9)	Q4 (M10-12)	Q1 (M13-15)	Q2 (M16-18)	Q3 (M19-21)	Q4 (M22-24)	Q1 (M25-27)	Q2 (M28-30)	Q3 (M31-33)	Q4 (M34-36)
WP2 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION	UPC	[Grid with stars in Q3 Year 1, Q3 Year 2, Q4 Year 2, Q4 Year 3, and Q4 Year 3]											
2.1 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION	UPC	[Grid with stars in Q3 Year 1, Q3 Year 2, Q4 Year 2, Q4 Year 3, and Q4 Year 3]											
2.2 DIGITAL MEDIA	SmartIO	[Grid with stars in Q2 Year 1 and Q3 Year 1]											
2.3 TECHNICAL ADVISORY GROUP	UPC	[Grid with star in Q2 Year 1]											
2.4 PARTICIPATION IN EC EVENTS AND ENGAGEMENT WITH EUROPEAN PROJECTS	SmartIO	[Grid]											
2.5 PROJECT EVENTS	UPC	[Grid]											

Figure 6: Work Package 2 planning

Under the T2.1, the WP2 has been active in creating the contents of C&D, organizing the project contribution in conferences, workshops, fairs, exhibitions, local meetings and scientific journals. During the first period, WP2 has been focused on creating the C&D tools (T2.2), specially the digital media tools like the website, social media accounts and videos. Additionally, the Technical Advisory Group (T2.3) has been constituted, and some descriptive videos of the project have been released. The project has been very active in the BRIDGE group (T2.4). Finally, the first INVADE large scale event is under preparation and it is scheduled for the 10/10/2018 in Oslo (T2.5).

The progress and results of each task are detailed below:

- T2.1 Dissemination and communication

The project has contributed to the scientific community with 6 conference papers and 1 journal paper. 7 new publications are under preparation and the rest of publications will come once the pilots are operative and results can be shown. Partners have contributed to the website with 43 posts. 3 workshops have been organized to create awareness of the project. Within this task, the flyer, poster, project presentation and the Zenodo repository were prepared as a dissemination tools for fairs, workshops and meetings. The open source plan detailed in D2.3 specifies which data and information will be public and allocated in the website and the Zenodo repository. All contents from INVADE project are linked to the INVADE community.

- T2.2 Digital media

The project is managing social media accounts in Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, LinkedIn and the Research Gate. Twitter and Facebook created many posts generating awareness of the project. Twitter is very dynamic creating interactions with people asking about the project. Facebook is more useful to disseminate website posts and other links.

Additionally, the first video preparations were located in this task and were ready by June.

- T2.3 Technical Advisory Group (TAG)

The Technical Advisory Group (TAG) is designed to gain additional technical expertise on R&D effort and demonstrations and have a more focused strategic vision. It will

include members from the most important types of stakeholders and high-level scientific researchers.

The creation of the TAG was one of the objectives of the first months of the project. For this purpose, a letter of invitation and a FAQ (Frequently Asked Questions) document were prepared to be sent to potential TAG candidates. The choice of the TAG candidates was a consensus among project partners.

The first TAG meeting was held in Barcelona on the 13th June 2017. The objective was to present the INVADE concept design and receive feedback from the TAG members. Project partners were very positive about the feedback received from the TAG members.

- T2.4 Participation in EC events and project clusters

Main goal for participating in EC events is the successful integration of INVADE into existing European projects landscape and fruitful contribution to events organised by the European Union bodies. INVADE consortium contributed to regulatory, research, policy formation sessions, and workshops or other events relevant to the European energy efficiency initiatives.

The main EC events were related to the BRIDGE cluster. INVADE is present in 4 working groups of this cluster: coordination, business models, regulation and customer engagement.

- T2.5 INVADE large scale events

In addition to all communication throughout the project lifetime there will also be held two large scale events during this period. Our goal is to target 100-150 participants at the actual events, further the content will be distributed on the website, to relevant press and medias and through all our Social Media channels in order to target a broader audience.

The first large-scale event was scheduled for June 2018. However, this June was full of exhibitions, fairs and workshops and the consortium decided to postpone it after summer holiday to reach a wider audience.

Deliverables from WP2 are:

- D2.1 Project website and social network profiles

The main purpose of D2.1 is to present the technical and editorial description of the INVADE website. The website will have the URL www.h2020invade.eu and serves as a news and information hub for the upcoming dissemination and communication tasks throughout the project period. This document describes the purpose of the site, the different templates for landing pages, the structure and functionality of the site, maintenance of the site, and how the overall communication and dissemination tasks are optimized by analysing and evaluating the ongoing results. Further D2.1 defines the INVADE social media platforms and accounts and describe how to bridge the gap between the channels in order to deliver well planned and structured quality content for the projects various stakeholders.

- D2.2 Dissemination plan

The D2.2 of INVADE project contains all information necessary to fulfil all communication and dissemination (C&D) objectives. The document describes the C&D actions, defines responsible partners and collaborators, provides guidelines about journal and congress publications, newsletters and press releases. Additionally, it provides an introduction about the activities repository that will help partners to fulfil the repository correctly. The EC events, the TAG and large-scale events guidelines are included in D2.2

- D2.3 Data management plan v1.0 and v2.0

The main purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to describe the characteristics of the data collected from research and real pilots. v1.0 settles the first version of the data management plan and v2.0 includes more details. The DMP has been elaborated following the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 including all sections.

- D2.4 Dissemination and communication intermediate report

This document reflects the dissemination and communication actions performed during the first half of the INVADE project. It reviews the measures and actions taken during the first and a half year for spreading the project objectives and evolution.

Deviations and impact on the task planning

- The Large-scale event was scheduled for June 2018 but has not been executed due to events overbooking during June.
- One newsletter was scheduled for the first year and half period. However, it has been postponed in order to include the initial pilot results and the early version of the INVADE integrated platform.
- The BRIDGE cluster has been the main focus of T2.4 but it cannot be the only cluster to be part of.

Proposed deviations corrective actions

- The large-scale event has been postponed to October 2018.
- The first newsletter will be launched during November 2018 including the deployment of the INVADE integrated platform in the pilots.
- Other EC events than BRIDGE will be detected during next months and the INVADE will contribute to them.

Role of partners

UPC is in charge of the work package coordination, tasks T2.1, T2.3 and T2.5, scientific publications coordination, events and fairs coordination, poster, project presentation and the final large-scale event.

SmartIO is in charge of tasks T2.2 and T2.4, of the webpage, flyer and video. Additionally, SmartIO will attend all the events organized by the commission for the coordination between the different founded projects in order to improve the coordination and to optimize the different outcomes of the projects increasing the overall impact. SmartIO is in charge of the first large-scale event in Norway.

NTNU, SmartIO, VTT and UPC are in charge of publishing the scientific results in conferences and peer-reviewed journals. Schneider Electric, eSmart, Albena, Lyse, Estabanell, Elaad and GreenFlux are in charge of publishing press releases, EC programme meetings and dissemination of project achievements.

1.2.3 Work package 3: Exploitation

Overall objectives of the work package

The exploitation effort organized by WP3 is meant to cater for the project's social and business impact. More precisely the work package aims to:

- Ensure an organic relationship between INVADE and the wider stakeholder community
- Increase awareness activities and results generated by INVADE
- Ensure optimum strategic positioning of INVADE within the wider domain it addresses
- To ensure that the INVADE initiative will have relevance to a broad range of stakeholders
- To prepare a solid business and exploitation plan and to discuss it with the stakeholders in order to have a relevant market product and ensure a firm deployment potential

The impact pursued with these objectives will be directed toward policy makers, end-users and end-user communities, standardisation bodies, public sector and industry representatives. It is important to solicit stakeholders that represent potential alliances which can enable cross-fertilisation between INVADE activities and others both in the beginning of the project as well as in preparing for exploitation of results and impact generation. It is also important to identify stakeholders that represent current barriers that must be mitigated or removed.

Overall progress at work package level.

The work carried out in WP2 in period 1 has been focused to meet the objectives specified in the DoA. It has been structured according to the following planned 10 s:

- T 3.1 Stakeholders Engagement Plan:
- T 3.2 Stakeholders analysis
- T 3.3 Business and Exploitation Plan
- T 3.4 Face-to-Face Consultations and dedicated workshops
- T 3.5 Exploitation Users

- T 3.6 Engagement with municipalities, communities and DSOs
- T 3.7 Life cycle analysis
- T 3.8 Contribution to Policy and Regulatory agendas
- T 3.9 Contribution to Standards
- T 3.10 Intellectual Property Rights management

	WP and Task leaders	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3			
		Q1 (M1-3)	Q2 (M4-6)	Q3 (M7-9)	Q4 (M10-12)	Q1 (M13-15)	Q2 (M16-18)	Q3 (M19-21)	Q4 (M22-24)	Q1 (M25-27)	Q2 (M28-30)	Q3 (M31-33)	Q4 (M34-36)
WP3 EXPLOITATION	SMARTIO												
3.1 STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT PLAN	SmartIO			★									
3.2 STAKEHOLDERS ANALYSIS	SmartIO					★							
3.3 BUSINESS AND EXPLOITATION PLAN	SmartIO									★			★
3.4 FACE TO FACE CONSULTATIONS AND DEDICATED WORKSHOPS	SmartIO												
3.5 EXPLOITATION USERS GROUP	SmartIO												
3.6 ENGAGEMENT WITH MUNICIPALITIES, COMMUNITIES AND ASSOCIATIONS	SmartIO												
3.7 LIFE CYCLE ANALYSIS	UPC									★			★
3.8 CONTRIBUTION TO POLICY AND REGULATORY AGENDAS	SmartIO												
3.9 CONTRIBUTION TO STANDARDS	ELAAD												
3.10 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS MANAGEMENT	SmartIO												

Figure 7: Work Package 3 planning

The progress and achievements of each task are highlighted in the following.

- T3.1 Stakeholders Engagement Plan

The work on this task was initiated at the very start of the project and will proceed until month 24. Its ambition was to define the perimeter of the INVADE project’s pertinent stakeholder perimeter. The basic questions to be answered which is related to this task are:

1. What type stakeholders can serve as enablers and alliances for the project and the project aims during and after the project?
 - a. In what way can they help and support the aims of the project?
 - b. How do the innovations produced in INVADE compare to others within the perimeter?
 - c. What role should they play in the context that INVADE defines?
 - d. In what way should they be engaged?

2. What type of stakeholders represent existing and potential barriers for the deployment and injection of INVADE results into future business and societal work?
 - a. What is the likely nature of such barriers?
 - b. How can they be avoided or worked around?

These questions have been answered in the first deliverable D3.1 which was completed in M6, but which is still maintained. The task developed and applied a new method that was successfully built on Michael Porter’s industrial cluster analysis. The method was described in a paper that was published in the CIRED 2018 Workshop. The result of this task has supported further work in WP3 but has also served as a guide for pilot owners and technology providers in the project in their effort to create a perspective on their future business during and after the project.

- T3.2 Stakeholders analysis

The INVADE stakeholders' analysis has been strongly connected to the former task. It has produced the first version of deliverable D3.2. This task has identified companies, individuals and organizations representing the different stakeholder types defined in task T3.1. This effort has been coordinated with WP9 efforts. The development of a viable business model for the use of the full INVADE platform as well as business models that can take advantage of parts of the platform or any other INVADE insight produced have been strongly influenced by the market review incorporated in the Stakeholder analysis. This has led to the definition of the specific INVADE ecosystem. It has also created awareness of the need to include various cloud-based and platform-based services as a part of the stakeholder group of which INVADE must align itself with. Moreover, the task has served, in cooperation with results from WP9, as a means to develop relevant business cases based on INVADE for the pilot owners in INVADE. Results from task T3.2 and D3.2 serve as an important base and reference for all other tasks in WP3.

- T3.3 Business and Exploitation Plan

Task T3.3 is a major effort and is at the heart of WP3. Its aim is to produce two deliverables which in turn embraces several other WP3 tasks too. Task T3.3 serves as the bridge between R&I and business development. Both internal and external stakeholders are addressed for this purpose. An action-oriented market review including both interviews, surveys, active market research and meetings have identified multiple “take away” possibilities for INVADE and its consortium members. These include a number of concrete cases in different countries:

- Property developers (Norway, Germany): Renewables, EVs, smart charging, V2G/B, stationary battery, hybrid forms of flexibility
- Parking house owners (Norway, Holland): Renewables, EVs, smart charging, V2G/B, stationary battery, hybrid forms of flexibility
- Smart city developers/municipalities (UK, Norway, Holland, Spain): EVs, smart charging, V2G/B, stationary battery, hybrid forms of flexibility
- Bus manufacturer (Holland): Electric buses, smart charging, V2G/B, stationary battery, hybrid forms of flexibility
- Hotel owners (Bulgaria): Renewables, EVs, smart charging, V2G/B, stationary battery, hybrid forms of flexibility
- Camping sites (Norway, Denmark): Renewables, EVs, smart charging, V2G/B, stationary battery, hybrid forms of flexibility
- Device manufacturers: Hybrid forms of flexibility
- DSOs (Norway, Renewables, EVs, smart charging, V2G/B, stationary battery, hybrid forms of flexibility
- TSOs (ENTSO-e, Romania, Albania, Bulgaria, Norway, Ireland): Hybrid forms of flexibility

- T3.4 Face-to-Face Consultations and dedicated workshops

Task T3.3 has served as basis for this effort. Task T3.4 will also inject results back into D3.3 and D3.6 “Final Business and Exploitation Plan” managed by the task T3.3. Stakeholders have been identified and they have been confronted with general prospects of the INVADE concept developed and the future business cases for partners. In return the project has harvested input pertinent for the design and engineering. both technical and business oriented. The process is still ongoing. Consultees so far include

representatives from Delta Electronics, DNV-GL, Skagerak Energi (N), NordPool, ENTSO-E, Fortum(FIN), Open Utility (UK), Statkraft and more. Some of these representatives have also been recruited for the Exploitation User Group (EUG). A first workshop on the topic of market trends, needs and possibilities for INVADE was held in Oslo on March 6, 2018.

- T3.5 Exploitation Users

The Exploitation User Group (EUG) has been growing steadily since the inception of WP3 activities in the project reaching 10 active members within the first 15 months. The March 6 event was the first time where they were challenged on how they see the future for INVADE and what should shape developments. The interest for INVADE has increased steadily and we have extended the membership limit of the EUG to 20. Invitations to EUG members to take part in the Major Event to be held in Oslo on October 6, 2018 has been extended. Here they will be asked to provide more input and constructive criticism on the project efforts. They will also cater for interviews undertaken in T3.4.

- T3.6 Engagement with municipalities, communities and DSOs

During the first year this task resided on connections before the project started. After EUG has been established more activities and communities have been involved. Important input has also been gathered during M15-M18 with the new German partner. Important input has been harvested from Hvaler, Bø, Sarpsborg and Stavanger municipality in Norway. Norwegian energy companies like Skagerak, Statkraft, Energi Norge, Agder Energi, Fredrikstad Energi have shared important insight, visions and data. Insights on potential impact has been harvested. Input from multiple households and EV drivers in Norway has been shaping work in both WP3 and WP9. Other individual and groups have been lined up for interviews and discussion on future embracement of INVADE results. Future involvement with end-user communities such as Øbo and Orut in Sweden, Noord Brabant, Tilburg, ENECO, Enexis in Holland, Iberdrola, Granollers in Spain and Freiburg in Germany. Input from these will also shape content in deliverable D3.3. Stakeholders representing both local DSO, business developers and local business communities have also been invited to an INVADE workshop for this purpose in Bulgaria on September 13. An important subject that has been discussed is where to demonstrate INVADE results beyond the pilot sites.

- T3.7 Life cycle analysis

Work on Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) has also progressed well. This task addresses environmental issues, hazards and resolves, of which must be emphasized during design, engineering and promotion of the project. The effort has been coordinated with similar work in WP6 (T6.4). The drafting of deliverable D3.4 “Life Cycle Analysis” is well underway.

- T3.8 Contribution to Policy and Regulatory agendas

The project has so far successfully attracted the attention of the Norwegian regulator and policy makers in the Netherlands and Norway at ultimate government level. WP3 is trying, in conjunction with WP2 efforts, to use these channels to influence similar institutional bodies in Europe. One achievement so far is the rejuvenation and influence

of the debate around local flexibility markets using the type of technologies that INVADE can demonstrate. Another input has been related to the definition of grid codes and the status and ownership of stationary batteries. WP3 in INVADE has shown how present tariff policies associated with batteries ruins important societal and business-related opportunities that could improve the exploitation possibilities for INVADE efforts. Preparation for the same type of dialog has also been made other places. Government agencies in Baden-Wurrtemberg and Bulgaria have been lined up.

- T3.9 Contribution to Standards

INVADE WP3 has through this task made an active contribution related to the open standards for V2G/B. One of the things that the project has already involved itself in is the hearing on the OCPP v2.0 standard and the promotion of the final release. Through consultations, dialogs and workshops WP3 has encouraged the accelerated adoption of standards that supports V2G/B i.e. ISO/IEC15118. For demand-response purposes OpenADR has been promoted and already we see the needs for extending this standard from the work that we are doing. Moreover, we see a need for extending and joining BIM and CIM to serve some of the purposes that INVADE targets. Aspect of this will already be highlighted in D3.3 due in M24.

- T3.10 IPR management

IPR management has been conducted. Guidance on how to treat IPR issues have been created. Especially the tension between business development, the need for competitive protection and publication of research have been addressed. Here input from the EU Commission itself has been used as well as input from patent bureau's like Zacco. Documentation of the overall IPR strategy will be included in D3.3.

Deviations and impact on the task planning

Currently there are none other than the fact that we have saved man hours for the latter part of the project as we wish to create a substantial overlap between internal business development and the project for project partners as well as their primary users and closest stakeholders.

Proposed deviations corrective actions

None, other than increasing activities with different internal external stakeholders as project results become more tangible and visible. Here cooperation with WP2 is required. Promotional and educating events are essential to achieve the needed engagement. So are demonstrations, hands-on experiences along with convincing cost-benefit analyses based on the pilot tests.

Role of partners

SmartIO has lead the work package. However, all partners have been engaged actively through meetings, interviews and self-driven contributions. ElaadNL has led the work on

standardisation and policy frameworks according to plan. UPC has championed the life cycle analysis and will assure the conclusion of D3.4. Finally, all partners has contributed to the business and exploitation plan development. The cooperation between Lyse, Greenflux and Schneider have been very instrumental in the rapid acceleration of the business related parts of WP3. Partner involvement has been achieved through continuous dialog, surveys and a major workshop in Copenhagen November 2017 where multiple business cases were discussed. It is important to point out that this part has involved business leaders and business developers at top organizational level and not only the people responsible for the day-to-day work in the project.

1.2.4 Work package 4: LSG Overall INVADE architecture

Overall objectives of the work package.

The main objectives of WP4 Overall INVADE architecture during period 1 have been to define the INVADE system architecture, which is the basis for the following development process. It includes the concept design of the INVADE system with a use cases description, the SGAM architecture specification, the definition of the software architecture of the flexibility cloud, and the adaptation of this general architecture to each pilot.

WP4 has generated the specifications of both the ICT platform and of the services it will provide. These specifications have been used in the development of the flexibility management operation in WP5 (Flexibility Management System), and in the development of the platform components for the communication infrastructure WP7 (Communication platform) and in the cloud tools in WP8 (Integrated INVADE platform).

Overall progress at work package level

The work carried out in WP4 in period 1 has been focused to meet the objectives specified in the DoA. It has been structured according to the following planned 5 tasks:

- T4.1 Concept design and use cases
- T4.2 SGAM Architecture
- T4.3 Flexibility Cloud software architecture
- T4.4 Standards and communication protocols
- T4.5 Architecture adaptation for pilots implementation.

	WP and Task leaders	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3			
		Q1 (M1-3)	Q2 (M4-6)	Q3 (M7-9)	Q4 (M10-12)	Q1 (M13-15)	Q2 (M16-18)	Q3 (M19-21)	Q4 (M22-24)	Q1 (M25-27)	Q2 (M28-30)	Q3 (M31-33)	Q4 (M34-36)
WP4 OVERALL INVADE ARCHITECTURE	UPC												
4.1 CONCEPT DESIGN AND USE CASES	UPC												
4.2 SGAM ARCHITECTURE	UPC												
4.3 FLEXIBILITY CLOUD SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE	Esmart												
4.4 STANDARDS AND PROTOCOLS	Elaad												
4.5 ARCHITECTURE ADAPTATION TO PILOT IMPLEMENTATIONS	UPC												
4.6 ARCHITECTURE REVIEW	UPC												

Figure 8: Work Package 4 planning

During this first period, on one hand, the development of T4.1, T4.2, T4.3 and T4.4 has led to the definition of the concept design and the INVADE system architecture. On the other hand, the execution of T4.5 has resulted in a proposal of adaptation of this generic architecture to each of the project pilots.

The progress and results of each task are detailed below:

- T4.1 Concept design and use cases

This task provided a general description of the system, which is the basis for the following implementation tasks. The task outputs included a review of the available flexibility management frameworks and how the flexibility operator role is defined in the INVADE project. Following, the flexibility services, flexibility sources and use cases are described. Then, a description of the flexibility sources and services that can provide more added value to each use case was done. In addition, the traffic light concept that determines which service has higher priority in each moment, the interface mechanisms with BRP/DSO and customers, and the baseline definition were described.

All this has been reflected in deliverable D4.1 Overall INVADE architecture.

- T4.2 SGAM Architecture

The aim of this task was to define the generic architecture of the INVADE system using the SGAM methodology. At first, it described generic components to be used in the general INVADE system in the component layer, without limitations on the available infrastructure at the pilot sites. Then, information, communication and function layers have been detailed.

All this has been reflected in deliverable D4.1 Overall INVADE architecture.

- T4.3 Flexibility Cloud software architecture

The aim of this task was to provide a detailed documentation of the software architecture to be deployed both for the testing and commercialisation purposes of INVADE. As a result, this task provided the specifications, features and requirements for the Flexibility Cloud software based on the outcome of the concept design.

All this has been reflected in deliverable D4.1 Overall INVADE architecture.

- T4.4 Standards and communication protocols

This task aims to analyse, up-take and improve on the existing communication standards and protocols on smart grids, with special focus on the standards in the e-mobility chain and the smart charging. During period 1, the goal of this task was identify the characteristics of EV related standards protocols, and providing information about the functionality of these protocols. This information was used as an input to define the communication layer in T4.5 and in WP74.3.

All this has been reflected in deliverable D4.1 Overall INVADE architecture.

- T4.5 Architecture adaptation for pilots' implementation

The aim of this task was to adapt the generic INVADE architecture described in D4.1 to each pilot. Outputs from previous tasks were used to choose the more suitable

components and communication systems for each of the pilot sites, as they are highly dependent on the characteristics of the electricity network and the area in which they are going to be implemented. This task also described the flexibility services, sources and roles that then are identified and defined for each of the pilots. The changes in the German pilot makes necessary to extent the duration of this task to update the description of the INVADE architecture for this pilot.

All this has been reflected in deliverable D4.2 INVADE architecture of pilots.

Deviations and impact on the task planning

The WP4 main pending issue is to review D4.2 to add the architecture of the new German pilot. Although a first version of D4.2 was submitted on time (M10), the overall progress is not completely satisfactory according to DoA, as some expected results from T4.5 are still pending regarding the new German pilot.

Proposed deviations corrective actions

Once Badenova was entirely integrated into the project, the creation of a task force is planned to try to speed up the definition of the architecture of the new German pilot. The objective of this task force is to identify flexibility services and sources, and to define roles, devices and communication protocols for the new German pilot. It will be formed by Badenova, UPC, Schneider, SmartIO and eSmart.

Role of Partners:

UPC is the work package leader and led tasks T4.1 Concept design and use cases, T4.2 SGAM Architecture and T4.5 Architecture adaptation for pilots implementation. Additional mainly insights were provided by Elaad, eSmart and Schneider based on their fields of expertise. eSmart led task T4.3 Flexibility Cloud software architecture, and Elaad led task T4.4 Standards and communication protocols.

Under the supervision of UPC, all project's partners participated in activities with their area of knowledge contributing to the definition of the INVADE concept design in T4.1. UPC led T4.2 with contributions from Schneider and Greenflux for the general component, information and communication SGAM layers. eSmart led the definition of the ICT platform architecture in task T4.3, with contributions from UPC, NTNU, VTT, Elaad and Greenflux. Through their expertise in standardisation, Elaad conducted the main activities in T4.5 with the collaboration of UPC, eSmart and Schneider. UPC led T4.5 with contributions from eSmart and Schneider. Partners related with the pilots (EPESA, Lyse, Albena, and GreenFlux) also contributed with their pilot's specifications.

1.2.5 Work package 5: Flexibility management system

Overall objectives of the work package

The focus of the work package 5 (WP5) is to assess flexibility and perform analysis in order to investigate the optimal deployment of flexibility sources. Solutions to reduce the challenges brought by variable RES and EV charging include both the added flexibility on the supply and load side. Combining the different characteristics of these resources is essential in assessing the value of distributed energy resources in the power system and in the energy market. The chief objective of this WP is to study how to achieve optimal deployment of flexible energy storage in distribution systems. This would lead to improved use of existing power system infrastructure and reduce issues caused by variable renewable energy sources in the physical electricity systems and at the electricity markets.

Overall progress at work package level

The progress during first period centres on developing flexibility operation and planning algorithms. Flexibility operation algorithm comprises the necessary methods and models for the development of initial integrated INVADE flexibility cloud platform. The platform serves the project pilots based on the framework described in D4.2.

Overall the WP is structured into 4 planned tasks according to DOA. The tasks provide solutions for successful practices to address the problem of flexibility management in RES dominated electricity system from different potential stakeholders. These tasks are:

- T 5.1 Analysis of the flexibility alternatives in distribution grids with high penetration of renewables and grid constraints
- T 5.2 Assessment of the potential value of alternatives in the future with demand growth from EVs, renewables integration and distributed storage units
- T 5.3 Energy storage units allocation/positioning and sizing algorithm (design and programming)
- T 5.4 Design and program the flexibility management operation algorithm

	WP and Task leaders	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3								
		Q1 (M1-3)	Q2 (M4-6)	Q3 (M7-9)	Q4 (M10-12)	Q1 (M13-15)	Q2 (M16-18)	Q3 (M19-21)	Q4 (M22-24)	Q1 (M25-27)	Q2 (M28-30)	Q3 (M31-33)	Q4 (M34-36)					
WP5 FLEXIBILITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS	NTNU																	
5.1 ANALYSE THE FLEXIBILITY ALTERNATIVES IN DISTRIBUTION GRIDS	NTNU			★														
5.2 ASSESSMENT OF THE POTENTIAL VALUE OF THE FLEXIBILITY ALTERNATIVES	NTNU				★													
5.3 ENERGY STORAGE UNITS ALLOCATION/POSITIONING ALGORITHM	NTNU					★												
5.4 DESIGN AND PROGRAM THE FLEXIBILITY MANAGEMENT ALGORITHM	NTNU													★				

Figure 9: Work Package 5 planning

The progress of each individual tasks is elaborated in the following sections.

- T 5.1 Analysis of the flexibility alternatives in distribution grids with high penetration of renewables and grid constraints

The main goal of this task is to carry out a study scope to identify a theoretical foundation and standard definition for necessary terminologies that can be used for remaining tasks in WP5. The task is concluded by D5.1. This document gives an overview of the main grid challenges caused by distributed generation, and how flexibility services from defined use cases in DOA can be utilized to revile such problems. In this context, we have reviewed official documents and the literature of power systems to address the problems caused by distributed energy resources (DER) and the solutions proposed to solve these issues. Moreover, the services for the distribution grid is discussed in relation

to the other uses of the batteries (such as transmission system operator (TSO) support and balancing responsible party (BRP) support) and limitations of use (e.g. due to the locational uncertainty of electrical vehicles (EVs) and driver range requirements). In this respect, the services that are most relevant to the INVADE project are identified.

The task is completed in M6 of the project, and the final deliverable, i.e., D5.1 is approved by TCC.

- T 5.2 Assessment of the potential value of alternatives in the future with demand growth from EVs, renewables integration and distributed storage units

The objective of the task is to evaluate the value of the flexibility alternatives that can be incorporated by distribution systems. The outcome of the activity is to provide an approach to assess their benefits. In this respect, D5.2. has been delivered. The purpose of this document is to describe and discuss possible methodologies and models that can be used for estimating the value of flexibility from mobile and stationary storages in distribution grids. The document serves as a basis for the modelling and assessments that is carried out in this task. This task continues in the second period.

- T 5.3 Energy storage units allocation/positioning and sizing algorithm (design and programming)

The task involves the optimal siting and sizing of the storage unit from the use case, application and grid operation point of view. This is important to ensure that the storage system can effectively contribute to the network management and mitigation of operating challenges.

During this period, a bi-level optimization approach is proposed and documented in D5.3b to address the siting-sizing decisions. We introduce a planning algorithm from different grid user perspectives. First, we focused on the prosumer perspective, where the operating objective function refers to the electricity bill minimization problem. Next, we focused on DSO point of view, where the installation of battery storage in the low/medium voltage level is an interesting alternative for grid reinforcement. The proposed algorithm has been implemented and tested on IEEE benchmark test system. The task is planned to continue in the second period.

- T 5.4 Design and program the flexibility management operation algorithm

This primary objective of this task is to investigate methodologies for effective management of flexible possibilities in distribution systems. The flexibility algorithms that will be implemented in the Integrated INVADE platform through the task T8.3 is documented in D5.3a. This document contains a description of the algorithms that will be used in the daily operations. A key finding in the document is that the way to model flexibility and how much value that can be extracted from the flexible sources are tightly connected to the amount of information that is available. The first running version of the flexibility algorithm using rolling and receding horizon in order to handle uncertainties and newly available information has been developed and tested. This model contains a subset of a flexibility operation algorithm that will be cooperated in INVADE platform.

Deviations and impact on the task planning

We have extended the activities of T5.2 until M24 since these activities are very much depending on the results of the algorithm implementation in T5.3 and T5.4, and both tasks are expected to continue until M24.

This deviation is expected to not have any negative impact on the other activities in INVADE Project. However, it will improve the outcomes of task T 5.2 significantly.

Proposed deviations corrective actions

n.a.

Role of Partners

NTNU leads the work package and is leading tasks T5.1 to T5.3. UPC leads task T5.4.

Both UPC and eSmart are heavily involved in developing and implementing of the flexibility operation algorithm. VTT is actively involved in battery models’ development. Partners from pilots, i.e., Schneider, Lyse, EPESA, Elaad and GreenFlux contribute by providing practical inputs with to improve the algorithms.

1.2.6 Work package 6: Energy storage technologies

Overall objectives of the work package

The work carried out in WP6 in the first period was focused to meet the objectives specified in the DoA. The task-structure and the original schedule of WP6 are shown in Figure 6.

WP and Task leaders	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3			
	Q1 (M1-3)	Q2 (M4-6)	Q3 (M7-9)	Q4 (M10-12)	Q1 (M13-15)	Q2 (M16-18)	Q3 (M19-21)	Q4 (M22-24)	Q1 (M25-27)	Q2 (M28-30)	Q3 (M31-33)	Q4 (M34-36)
WP6 ENERGY STORAGE TECHNOLOGIES	VTT											
6.1 STORAGE SYSTEM DIMENSIONING AND DESIGN			★									
6.2 BATTERY STATE OF HEALT AND LIFETIME						★			★			
6.3 BATTERY TECHNO-ECONOMICS AND OPTIMAL OPERATION						★			★			
6.4 BATTERY SAFETY AND LIFECYCLE MANAGEMENT												
6.5 PILOT SPECIFIC RESEARCH SUPPORT												

Figure 10: Work Package 6 planning

In the first period, the main focus was initially in the development of the methodology and tools for the dimensioning and selection of the storage systems. The focus then gradually shifted to the development of battery ageing models and state-of-health diagnostics methods (T6.2) as well as battery-modelling in the optimization framework (T6.3). During M13-M18 the lifecycle management of batteries (T6.4) has got much effort, as the work for the LCA of the pilot battery storages was initiated and a close collaboration with WP3/T3.7 was agreed. WP6 will contribute the LCA for pilot batteries, and WP3 will use these results as an input for the LCA of the pilots (D3.4 and D3.5). The tasks T6.2 and T6.4 were extended until M36 to be in line with the timeline of T3.7 and D3.5.

The main outcomes of the WP were the deliverables D6.1 *Storage system dimensioning and design tool (M6)*, D6.2 *Battery techno-economics tool (M15)*, and D6.3 *Simplified state of health diagnostics tool (M15)*, which were submitted on time, and the selection and procurement of the storage systems of the pilots in collaboration with WP10. In

addition, a workshop on grid integration of battery storages was organised, publications were submitted, and two presentations at conferences were given.

The progress and results of each task are detailed below:

- T6.1 Storage system dimensioning and design

The focus during the first period was in the development of the necessary tools and in the selection and procurement of the storage systems for the pilots. The task provided a generic methodology for the dimensioning and selection of the battery storage system for the pilots. This methodology includes, e.g., duty cycle analysis, requirements definition, performance assessment tools, review of commercial battery technologies, screening of potential battery suppliers, and techno-economic evaluations of different battery technologies for the pilots.

The main results that were obtained during the first five months have been reflected in deliverable D6.1 *Storage dimensioning and design tool*.

- T6.2 Battery state of health and lifetime

During the first period, this task focused on gathering battery lifetime data and knowledge of the degradation stress factors from the literature and battery manufacturers. A database of the reported lifetime of batteries under different stress factors was formed, and a battery lifetime model including several degradation stress factors was developed. This model can be used in the lifetime prediction of batteries under certain load profiles and stress factors, and therefore, it contributes to the storage dimensioning and techno-economic assessments. Moreover, the obtained models for the degradation stress factors play an important role in the battery degradation model in the optimization framework to be implemented in the INVADE controller algorithm by WP5 and WP8.

In addition to lifetime modelling, also online state-of-health diagnostic methods were reviewed, and the most promising methods were identified and implemented in the laboratory. However, their suitability in real-world use was not evaluated yet, because there were no data available from the pilots.

The main results of this task have been reflected in *D6.3 State of health diagnostics tool*.

- T6.3 Battery techno-economics and optimal operation

During the first period, this task focused on developing tools for techno-economics and optimal operation of battery storages in the pilots. These tools are needed in WP5, WP8, T6.1, and T6.4. A battery model for the optimization framework was developed, and a set of generic constraints on the usage of the battery were defined in order to ensure good performance and accurate results of the optimization algorithm. Moreover, optimal operating conditions for batteries were defined in order to achieve long lifetime. Much effort was put on the development of the modelling method for the cost of degradation of a battery in the optimization framework. The main outcome of the task was a generic methodology for modelling and parameter extraction in the optimization framework and a set of parameters for the battery storage systems of the pilots.

The main results of this task have been reflected in *D6.2 Battery techno-economics tool*.

- T6.4 Battery safety and lifecycle management

During the first period, this task focused on the battery safety issues and the associated end-of-life criteria as well as on the second-life use of batteries, recycling, and LCA. Extensive literature review, including battery testing standards for automotive and industrial use, was conducted.

The LCA was initiated by defining the system boundaries and the methodology. Moreover, close collaboration with T3.7/UPC was initiated and a distribution of work was defined. A database of generic secondary data of batteries was formed, and an input data questionnaire for the pilots was prepared. Meetings with the first pilots have been held.

The main results of this task have been reflected in *D6.3 State of health diagnostics tool*. The results regarding the LCA will be published in future publications.

- T6.5 Pilot specific research support

During the first period, the main focus of this task was to collect data for duty cycle analysis to be used in the simulations and dimensioning of storages. Furthermore, this data was used in performance simulations, optimization simulations, and lifetime predictions of pilot battery storage systems.

Deviations and impact on the task planning

WP6 requested an extension of tasks T6.2 and T6.4 until the end of the project, i.e., M36. An amendment has been filed by the PC. The reasoning for the extension is twofold:

1. WP6 will be co-operating with T3.7 to provide LCA of the pilots. T6.4 performs the LCA of batteries and, as an output, provides LCA data of pilots' batteries for T3.7. Therefore, T6.4 should be extended for the timeline to be consistent with T3.7 (M6-M36) and D3.5 Final Life Cycle Analysis (M36).
2. The extension of T6.2 would enable more effort for the lifetime prediction of batteries by using real data from the pilots. T6.2 will provide data for lifetime assessment of pilot batteries. Expected lifetime has a high impact on the LCA of batteries, and thus, on the LCA of the pilots.

Proposed deviations corrective actions

No further actions are needed. Extension of T6.2 and T6.4 has been requested, and an amendment has been filed by the PC. Close collaboration and coordination with T3.7 / UPC regarding LCA of the pilots has been started in the beginning of 2018, and it will be continued until the end of the project. Close collaboration with the pilot owners is needed as well. High level of commitment by the pilots is needed to get proper input for the LCA.

Role of Partners:

VTT leads all tasks and activities in WP6.

NTNU gives insight and contributes to T6.1 and T6.3 mostly related to the battery sizing, techno-economics and modelling-related issues regarding the optimization algorithms.

Partners related with the pilots (Albena, EPESA, NewEn, and Schneider) contribute with their expertise in the fields of grids, pilot systems, and energy storages and their anticipated use cases and mission profiles.

1.2.7 Work package 7: Communication platform

Overall objectives of the work package

The aim of this WP is to provide full bidirectional communication between the underlying Physical Layer (PL) and the Cloud based software-based business Process Layer (BPL).

To specify the technical solutions and communications and protocol/interfaces between DERs / RTUs / Scada and Cloud.

- Provide a secure communication channel between the BPL and the PL
- Provide a well-defined and complete Application Programmers Interface (API) to the BPL.
- Provide a well-defined and complete API to the BPL for sending control signals to the PL

These objectives require that the Communication Platform (CP) has a well-defined functional interface with all kinds of Distributed Energy Resources (DER) and any equipment connected to these DERs. Thus, the CP will be able to read any kind of relevant sensors and meters and store such values in a suitable database which is accessible from the BPL through

Overall progress at work package level

WP and Task leaders	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3			
	Q1 (M1-3)	Q2 (M4-6)	Q3 (M7-9)	Q4 (M10-12)	Q1 (M13-15)	Q2 (M16-18)	Q3 (M19-21)	Q4 (M22-24)	Q1 (M25-27)	Q2 (M28-30)	Q3 (M31-33)	Q4 (M34-36)
WP7 COMMUNICATION PLATFORM	SCHNEIDER											
7.1 COMMUNICATIONS SPECIFICATION PLAN			★									
7.2 SPECIFICATION OF THE CP-API							★					
7.3 FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS OF BPL AND FIELD DEVICES INTEGRATION											★	
7.4 COMMUNICATIONS TEST PLAN, TEST AND TEST REPORT												

Figure 11: Work Package 7 planning

At WP7 level, main progress related to the activities has been to conclude tasks T7.1 and T7.2 with their corresponding deliverables.

A specifications plan has been defined and established for the communications that will take place in the project between the physical level (field devices) and the business layer (INVADE Platform).

The communications protocols necessary to carry out this communication have been defined as well as a specific communication plan for each pilot in the project.

In addition to defining the types of communications that can appear in each of the pilots, a list of communication use cases have been defined, in reference to the different technologies that will be implemented (EV, Storage, PV and Households - buildings).

Apart from to the aforementioned, a series of API's has been developed to establish bidirectional communication between each device of each pilot and the INVADE platform. Always according to the flexibility use cases defined in WP4.

- T7.1 Communications Specification Plan

Getting deeper into more details about the above introduction:

The deliverable D7.1 examines the communication requirements of the envisaged INVADE communication Layer establishing the steps and baseline to be followed in following tasks and WPs related with the Pilot developments, regarding all communication issues.

It has been defined the architecture to be followed, always according to the SGAM architecture defined in WP4.

Figure 12: Architecture of the INVADE system

The communication Layer is situated on the second level, which corresponds to zones b, c and d (field, station and operations). This layer defines the data exchange process between the different field devices and INVADE integration Platform. This data will be treated and used by different software applications which are developed in the project apart from the INVADE Platform (Third Level) (SGAM - e Level: Enterprise).

These applications will connect with the INVADE integrated Platform by using the CP-API's defined and established in D7.2.

A list of protocols has been defined to establish a correct communications path for all the data from physical devices to the Cloud Services.

- IEC 60870-5-101
- IEC 60870-5-104
- IEC-61850
- Modbus (TCP or RS-485)
- OCPP
- OCPI
- OSCP

General procedures have also been identified for each pilot in order to separate the different type of communication that will be involved in these cases.

Bulgaria

- Local Smart Meter (PMx) ↔ RTU (EGx100): Modbus Protocol
- RTU ↔ SCADA: Ethernet TCP
- SCADA ↔ INVADE Platform: Web Services

Spain

- SCADA ↔ RTU: IEC60870-5-104
- RTU ↔ Analyzer, Protections and Field Devices: Modbus RS-485
- RTU ↔ Power electronics: Modbus RS-485
- Power electronics ↔ BMS
- SCADA ↔ I NVADE Platform: web Service

The Netherlands

- DER ↔ SM (Smart Meter) Specific Protocols
- SM ↔ INVADE Platform
- SM ↔ Greenflux/Elaad Cloud Software
- STORAGE ↔ Greenflux/Elaad Cloud Software
- EV CHARGERS ↔ Greenflux/Elaad Cloud Software: OCPP protocol (OCPP 1.6 or Higher).
- Greenflux/Elaad Cloud Software ↔ INVADE Platform

Norway

- DER ↔ SM (Smart Meter) : Specific from Local controller
- SM ↔ INVADE Platform
- SM ↔ Home Automation Cloud Software
- STORAGE ↔ Home Automation Cloud Software
- EV CHARGERS ↔ Home Automation Cloud: OCPP
- Home Automation cloud ↔ INVADE Platform: Web Services

Germany

- Electricity consumers ↔ Smart Meter (Delivery and Consumption meter)
- Production Meter (PM) ↔ Smart Meter (SM)
- PM ↔ Inverter
- Storage ↔ Inverter
- Storage ↔ Management INVADE Platform
- INVADE platform ↔ Smart Meter (SM)

Besides defining the communication between actors involved, use cases were defined in a general way in order to cover all the possibilities in the pilots:

- EV charging station
- Storage
- Generation
- Household

For each use case, a conditions table was defined.

Use Case ID:	UC-1-EV_Ch
Use Case Name:	EV charging station communicating with the INVADE Integration Platform
Actors:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EV charging station/point - INVADE Integration Platform
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cloud Platform (Greenflux / Lyse / Estabanell)
Description:	<p>This UC describes the information exchanged between the INVADE platform and the EV charger (EV_Ch). The EV_Ch has to send the information to the INVADE platfor using another software (Greenflux in Netherlands or Home automation cloud in Norway).</p> <p>According to the charger capabilities, the system can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Receive active power consumed or generated - Receive reactive power, inductive or capacitive - Read other variables.
Pre-conditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EV owner parks in the EV_Ch and plug it. - The owner identifies its needs and is authorised - EV owner has established the needed contract with its conditions - The EV_Ch is connected to the main supply
Post-conditions:	<p>During the charge or discharge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The EV_Ch modifies its energy consumed/generated - The EV_Ch modifies its power factor
Information exchanged:	<p>INVADE Platform → Charger</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electrical state variables set-points <p>Charger → INVADE Platform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electrical state variables measurements - Charging power - Charging range capacity
Exceptions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No valid identification - No communications available
Assumptions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The EV owners will have an ID card to access the charger functionalities. - The charger dashboard will permit to access other external EV owners with their credit card. - The EV owner will send its requirements through a dashboard in the charging point or through its mobile phone.

Table 2: EV Use Case

- T7.2 Specification of the CP-API

Apart from the Communication Specification Plan, another big progress was made regarding the CP-API.

The deliverable D7.2 “Specification of the CP-API” is highly important for the correct ongoing of the project. This deliverable establishes the connection paths between the pilots and the INVADE platform. That’s to say, all the API’s functions are described in this deliverable, so each pilot needs to make the connector for sending all the data according to the API formats described in D7.2.

The asset management API specified is provided so an external system can manage the asset repository related to the context of the pilot.

Within the IIP we need to understand a logical topology of the assets in order for us to be able to perform predictions and optimizations. For each pilot this needs to be configured within the platform. There have been defined two approaches for this:

- The data can be provided via the asset management API, this has the advantage that if this interface is built it can be easily adjusted during the pilots and alternative configurations analysed.
- Or alternatively the data can be provided by supplying the pilot configuration data in an Excel template, and eSmart will facilitate the load this data into the platform. The template will be sent separately.

Assets are modeled as either areas or resources as shown below.

Figure 13: Relationships between Area, Sites and Resource Assets

All the API's have been related with the flexibility use cases defined in WP4, regarding all the messages exchanges between Flexibility operator and end users or clients.

- T7.3 Feasibility analysis and BPL field devices integration

Some preliminary studies have been done and they will be upgraded in the final results. Different elements involved in the communications platform are been studied and analysed, from field devices to business layer, including the INVADE platform, always taking the SGAM architecture as a starting point.

This task will end with the deliverable D7.3 in the second period.

- T7.4 Communications test plan, test and test report

Task T7.4 is still pending for a further development, just some initial Test template has been proposed to carry out at the end of the Wp timeline, once the INVADE CP-API have been achieved. Test Plan, and report is supposed to be the final step for the API connectors defined in D7.2 for the different pilots to prove that it has been established a real communications between INVADE platform and each Pilot System.

Deviations and impact on the task planning

n.a

Proposed deviations corrective actions

n.a

Role of partners

Schneider is the WP leader, with eSmart as main partner in developing the interface for the CP-API between the INVADE platform and each pilot system. eSmart has provided a description of the API-functions that are needed from the BPL and a specification of the desired results in the PL of such API-functions.

The rest of partners are the pilot owners which are involved in the developing of the connectors.

1.2.8 Work package 8: Integrated INVADE platform

Overall objectives of the work package

WP8 Integrated INVADE platform will deliver the cloud-based Integrated INVADE platform, which will be used by the Flexibility Operator (FO) to maximize the uptake of renewable energy in the grid. More specifically, the FO will use the Integrated INVADE platform to deliver flexibility services from flexibility vendors to flexibility customers.

The platform will be utilized at the pilot sites during the pilot phase of the project. Through the dashboard, the FO will among others be able to visualise historic and forecasted consumption and production at pilot sites and run optimization algorithms to assess optimal use of available flexibility.

The technical architecture defined in WP4 and the communication platform API defined in WP7 are important input to the WP. Furthermore, the flexibility algorithms specified in WP5, battery models from WP6 and business models and energy market structures from WP9 provides important input to the functionality and intelligence in the Integrated INVADE platform.

	WP and Task leaders	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3							
		Q1 (M1-3)	Q2 (M4-6)	Q3 (M7-9)	Q4 (M10-12)	Q1 (M13-15)	Q2 (M16-18)	Q3 (M19-21)	Q4 (M22-24)	Q1 (M25-27)	Q2 (M28-30)	Q3 (M31-33)	Q4 (M34-36)				
WP 8: INTEGRATED INVADE PLATFORM	ESMART																
8.1 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE FLEXIBILITY CLOUD ARCHITECTURE	Esmart																
8.2 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE FLEXIBILITY CLOUD CONTROL ARCHITECTURE	Esmart																
8.3 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE FLEXIBILITY CLOUD FLEXIBILITY MANAGEMENT ALGORITHMS, FUNCTIONS AND MONITORING CONTROL DASHBOARDS	Esmart							★		★				★			★
8.4 INTEGRATION OF ELECTRIC VEHICLES IN THE FLEXIBILITY CLOUD	GreenFlux																
8.5 TESTING AND VALIDATION OF THE INVADE PLATFORM AND ITS COMPONENTS IN THE TEST-LAB ENVIRONMENT	UPC																
8.6 DEVELOPMENT OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS FOR INVADE USERS	Esmart									★				★			

Figure 14: Work Package 8 planning

Overall progress at work package level.

The main outcomes in WP8 during the first period were the deliverables D8.1 Cloud based flexibility management system: Flexibility Cloud, phase 1, D8.2 Cloud based flexibility management system: Flexibility Cloud, phase 2 and D8.3 End-user mobile apps and management dashboards, phase 1.

D8.1 and D8.2 are both reports which combined describe the first version of the implemented Integrated INVADE platform. D8.3 is the first version of the Integrated INVADE platform software. On an overall level, the platform consists of a set of main processes which can be seen in the figure below. These processes, their built-in functionality and the link between them, constitutes the INVADE platform.

Figure 15: Overview of the main processes in the INVADE platform

The progress and results of each task are detailed below:

- T8.1 Implementation of the flexibility cloud architecture

The flexibility cloud architecture for the first version of the Integrated INVADE platform was developed in this task during the first period. The INVADE platform architecture described in D4.1 Overall INVADE architecture and in D4.2 INVADE architecture of pilots constitutes important input into the architecture specification.

The main results from this task are presented in D8.1 Cloud based flexibility management system: Flexibility Cloud, phase 1.

- T8.2 Implementation of the Flexibility cloud control architecture

In this task, the flexibility cloud control architecture for the first version of the Integrated INVADE platform was implemented. For the first period, this constitutes the processes Master data and configurations, Meter value management and Events and external information. The control signals management will be implemented in the second period of the project.

The main results from this task are presented in D8.1 Cloud based flexibility management system: Flexibility Cloud, phase 1 and D8.2 Cloud based flexibility management system: Flexibility Cloud, phase 2.

- T8.3 Implementation of the Flexibility Cloud flexibility management algorithms, functions, and monitoring & control dashboards

This task has focused on implementing the flexibility algorithms received from WP5, in addition to the functionality needed to provide, receive and display the necessary input and output from the flexibility algorithms. This includes the main processes Contract management, Predictions and Flexibility management optimization.

The main results from this task are presented in D8.2 Cloud based flexibility management system: Flexibility Cloud, phase 2.

- T8.4 Integration of Electric Vehicles in the Flexibility Cloud

This task focuses on how electric vehicles (EVs) can be implemented in the INVADE platform. The focus here has been two-fold: It has been analysed which information

relevant for the flexibility algorithms, that is possible to get from EVs, and it has been developed new communication protocols to support the integration of EVs in the INVADE platform. The new OCMP protocol, which will be used in the Dutch pilot, is an Invade pilot specific version of OSCP protocol.

The main results from this task are presented in D8.2 Cloud based flexibility management system: Flexibility Cloud, phase 2.

- T8.5 Testing and validation of the INVADE platform and its components in the test-lab environment

The activities in this task has centralized on specifying the cases to be tested in the test lab-environment. It has been decided to focus the testing on the prosumer flexibility services and to replicate a real pilot setup. This to ensure that the test is as close to a real setting as possible. The actual testing is scheduled to take place in the second period of the project.

The main results from the laboratory testing will be presented in the coming D8.4 Cloud based flexibility management system: Flexibility Cloud, phase 3.

- T8.6 Development of mobile applications for INVADE users

The INVADE platform version 1 focused on the prosumer flexibility services for the Norwegian and Dutch pilots. In these pilots, mobile applications from the pilot owners will be used. The question of developing INVADE mobile applications and dashboards will also be addressed for the remaining pilots and flexibility users and sellers.

Deviations and impact on the task planning

The original plan included laboratory testing of the Integrated INVADE platform prior to the pilot phase. As it has been decided to replicate a real pilot setup in the testing to ensure that the test is as close to a real setting as possible, the laboratory testing must be delayed compared to original plan. This because the interface between chosen pilot site and the Integrated INVADE platform need to be specified first. The testing is therefore scheduled to take place in the beginning of the pilot phase. Still, the testing is seen as useful to unveil possible problems and errors in the platform early in the pilot phase.

Proposed deviations corrective actions

n.a.

Role of Partners

WP8 is headed by eSmart and the company is task leader for tasks T8.1, T8.2 and T8.3. eSmart is through this responsible for the implementation of the Integrated INVADE platform. The other two project participants which have significant resources in the WP is UPC and GreenFlux. GreenFlux is task leader for T8.4 which involves integrating EVs into the platform. UPC is responsible for T8.5 which covers testing and validation of the INVADE platform in a testing laboratory.

1.2.9 Work package 9: Business models and energy market structures

Overall objectives of the work package

The primary objective of this work package is to develop innovative business models for energy storage in distribution networks in order to maximise impact of the INVADE project. This main objective is broken down into several sub-objectives:

- Understand existing business models in the field and their structure.
- Define value creation and propositions to customers, risks, critical resources, cost structures and stakeholders for specific business models.
- Define parameters for classification of business models in order to secure a well-structured business case landscape.
- Understand the significance of “soft” factors, i.e. ones that are hard to directly quantify, such as consumer’s behavioural preferences or urge for self-reliance.

Overall progress at work package level

WP9 consists of 4 tasks:

	WP and Task leaders	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3			
		Q1 (M1-3)	Q2 (M4-6)	Q3 (M7-9)	Q4 (M10-12)	Q1 (M13-15)	Q2 (M16-18)	Q3 (M19-21)	Q4 (M22-24)	Q1 (M25-27)	Q2 (M28-30)	Q3 (M31-33)	Q4 (M34-36)
WP 9: BUSINESS MODELS AND ENERGY MARKET STRUCTURES	LYSE												
9.1 REVIEW OF STATE-OF-THE-ART	SmartIO				★								
9.2 USER PRACTISES AND BEHAVIOUR ANALYSIS	NTNU								★				★
9.3 LOCAL POLICY AND REGULATIONS IMPLICATIONS	Elaad							★					
9.4 BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT AND CLASSIFICATION	Lyse									★			★

Figure 16 Work Package 9 planning

- T9.1 Review of state-of-the art.

What’s out there and can be relevant in an emerging new energy system? This was the main headline dominating work in T9.1. The task conducted the bulk of its activity during the first 9 months of the project. The work consisted of four basic elements; a state-of-the-art (SOTA) analysis of existing business models, an analysis of new and emerging business models, an analysis of energy and storage business models and relevant examples of companies that use new business models.

The process in T9.1 has revealed that Europe has come far with respect to technology, but is seriously lagging behind US and Asia with respect to business model innovation. In particular, Europe is weak with respect to the new and highly disruptive multi-sided business models seen at companies like Apple, Facebook, Alibaba, Tesla and more.

For this reason, WP9 and WP3 see the INVADE project as being instrumental in recognizing that “platform” no longer means “technology platform” only, but truly embraces the idea that technology platform and platform based business models are equally important and should therefore be developed in parallel and in close collaboration.

The task concluded with D 9.1 Review of existing business models and storage technology database Its main recommendations are:

- Business models should be of the platform type, multi-sided and customer-centric

- Business models should enable network effects and be able to absorb exponential digital growth mechanisms
 - Business models should foster open ecosystems with focus on APIs
 - Business models should reflect the most recent trends in both technological and societal developments - e.g., the ones related to digitalization, advanced analytics, complexity, customer preferences.
- T9.2 User practises and behaviour analysis

Understanding user behaviour in the energy market is crucial when trying to exploit findings expected in projects such as INVADE. Therefore T9.2 from early on planned its effort based on close contact with the 5 pilot tasks in WP10. The different use cases and how the pilots are organised and put together form a basis for collecting and analysing data from the pilot locations. As soon as the pilots are up and running, T9.2 will conduct user studies respectively.

Task leader NTNU has worked closely, not only with the pilot tasks, but also with WP3 and WP4, specifically input on user behaviour and technology domestication amongst pilot users.

T9.2 is responsible for 2 deliverables, of which the first was submitted in this period: D 9.2 Input on user behaviour and technology domestication amongst users to the business model development. The deliverable aims at providing knowledge and insight to the design and deployment of business models and smart energy technologies. It provides recommendations in four sections on 1) intervention and feedback, 2) introducing new technology, 3) segmentation and tariffs, and 4) vehicle to grid.

Among the findings:

- Novel information from feedback and monitoring devices may become the root cause of a new, more cemented consumption baseline, possibly leading to new barriers of behaviour change.
 - New monitoring devices in the household initially open a window for social learning. After learning has happened, devices fade into the background. After saturation is reached intervention becomes more cost intensive.
 - If routine change during the initial phase of solution domestication does not happen, changes will likely dissipate.
 - Attention must be paid to symbolic aspects of microgeneration. Some users are above all oriented towards “doing the right thing” (environmental or societal motivation).
- T9.3 Local policy and regulation implications

In order, not only to work out a recommended approach for business modelling, but also to conduct key tasks in other parts of the project, a basic overview of the relevant regulatory ramifications in the pilot markets is necessary. For this purpose task leader ElaadNL formed a questionnaire template in order to map universal traits in the 5 countries; The Netherlands, Norway, Germany, Bulgaria and Spain. EV car markets and storage regulation differ greatly among these countries – leading to a somewhat more comprehensive set of data being collected from Norway and the Netherlands as opposed to the others, particularly Bulgaria.

The bulk of the T9.3 responsibilities were carried out within this reporting period, leading up to D9.3: Report on legal policy implications

Here, T9.3 subsequently identifies possible solutions for the most important and urgent regulatory bottlenecks. In this way, both market and government are assisted with concrete ideas in order to accelerate the development of Smart Charging in the short term. The study also provides a starting point for the design of an efficiently and effectively functioning charging and storage market. The most pressing issue when it comes to battery storage in a regulatory context seems to be the role of the grid operator, specifically when it comes to battery ownership/operation.

- T9.4 Business model development and classification

This task bases parts of its work on findings and recommendations from the preceding tasks in addition to activities running with other work packages, particularly WP3 and WP10. The chosen business model definition is Alexander Oesterwalder's: "A business model describes how you create, deliver and capture value".

From early on during the first months, it became more and more obvious in order to have the necessary impact, that the process would be best served by letting T9.4 run in parallel with the pilot tasks instead of – as envisaged – following the findings in the pilots. That is why Lyse as task leader arranged several workshops and meeting with the pilot tasks in order to benefit from early pre-pilot engagement.

Another crucial choice of approach is to emphasize platform-based business models, as pointed out in D9.1.

T9.4 has also covered some dissemination activities, including writing a paper on business models together with WP3.

Although its deliverables D9.4 and D9.6 are due in the next reporting periode, T9.4 has already started preparations for an early issue of D9.4 (Set of INVADE business models including claddification framework simplified) in order for it to impact the pilots.

Activity has been progressing in all tasks on 3 main levels:

- Internally
In addressing interdependencies between tasks, e.g. as task T9.4 needs input from both behaviour analysis and regulatory questions in order to produce meaningful results.
- In close cooperation with other work packages, particularly WP3 on exploitation and WP 10, the pilot task.
- In order to submit deliverables of expected quality and on time.

All deliverables were submitted on time. A series of workshops, telcoms and meetings were carried out in order to facilitate the work process with particularly active participation from related tasks in work packages 3 and 10.

Deviations and impact on the task planning

n.a.

Proposed deviations corrective actions

n.a.

Role of partners

SmartIO was instrumental in putting together the SoA deliverable D9.1 with contributions from Lyse. In task 9.2, NTNU worked closely with Lyse and SmartIO on technology domestication and user behaviour patterns, noting that Lyse has broad energy customer exposure. Task 9.3 was headed by Elaad. Leading up to D9.3, contributions were valuable from SmartIO, specifically on storage/battery regulation. SmartIO was also able to fill the gap on relevant German information during the process of changing the German pilot task leader. Lyse, together with Albena and EPESA also contributed input on regulation from Norway, Bulgaria and Spain.

In task T9.4, significant contribution materialised from SmartIO. In addition, all 5 pilot task partners were able to contribute in order to put the business modelling process and the pilot activities on parallel tracks.

1.2.10 Work package 10: Pilots

Overall objectives of the work package

The main objectives of this WP 10 are to develop, prepare and connect the different pilots for test, demonstration and validation of the defined use-cases. The INVADE platform will be connected, tested and validated in five different countries for this specified four pilot use cases (PUCs), proving the value of active connected EV's and battery storage in the grid:

The WP 10 main objectives are to:

- To develop the pilots technically to support the business aspects and the defined architecture described within other WPs in this project.
- To connect the pilots to communicate with the INVADE-cloud, including local and central smartness.
- To run tests, evaluate, adjust and retest defined test-cases, based on the use-cases.

The different defined use-cases to be demonstrates is defined by pilots:

Pilot	PUC-1	PUC-2	PUC-3	PUC-4
Norway - Lyse	X		X	(x)
The Netherlands – Greenflux/ElaadNL	X			
Bulgaria - Albena	X	X		
Spain - EYPESA		X		
Germany - badenova				X

Table 3: Use-Case overview by pilot

PUC.1: Mobile energy storage using EVs for V2G, V2B and V2H operations

The use case involves mobile energy storage using EVs with focus on V2G, V2B and V2H operations along with higher renewable integration. This use case will demonstrate a link to the transport sector using renewable energy sources in each pilot site. Emphasis in PUC-1 has been placed on smart charging by means of schedules with the possibility of reverse flow. Use of more novel more experimental entities that have not reached the industry yet will be limited.

PUC 2: Centralised energy storage using an array of batteries at the sub-station or street level

The use case involves a centralized energy storage unit comprised of an array of smaller batteries at the substation and/or community level. This use case will demonstrate the applicability of large scale centralized storage units at the substation/street level to demand side management, power quality improvement, power peak-shaving and emergency back-up operations.

PUC 3: Distributed energy storage using individual batteries at the household level

The use case focus on distributed energy storage units spread across multiple households. The use case will showcase the benefits of distributing storage units across households.

There is another special case included inside PUC-3 which is one of the cases in Norway where households and smart devices will be treated.

Smart EV-charger or storage is included. INVADE Integration platform will connect remotely with these smart devices and will establish a bidirectional communication in order to collect all the electrical information and send control signal to them.

PUC 4: Hybrid level energy storage solutions addressing a combination of use case 2 and 3

This use case implements a hybrid/combination of centralized and distributed energy storage units at both substation/street and household levels (a combination of use cases 2 and 3).

Pilot Use Cases

The goal of the INVADE Project Pilots is to implement and manage the external influences on the grid and prevent the grid from failure caused by fluctuating loads and feed-in. The pilots will attempt to show that EVs and batteries can play major roles to level out and effectively utilize the capacity in the infrastructure while avoiding congestions and reduced quality of supply. Batteries/EV's are assumed to be the most suitable resources for flexibility management in the distribution grid. In addition, EVs represents a capacity challenge itself due to increasing power demands that accumulate unfavourable peaks. Proper management of EV charging thus serves a dual purpose. Connected to the INVADE-cloud these resources will play a major role in the future.

Large Scale

Each pilot will also be prepared for a largescale roll-out. It will be very important to show efficient ways to scale-up the pilots without redesign or re-develop the basic systems in the pilots/models. Easy scalability is a key-word in INVADE.

For these purposes, WP10 have been divided in 8 tasks:

	WP and Task leaders	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3				
		Q1 (M1-3)	Q2 (M4-6)	Q3 (M7-9)	Q4 (M10-12)	Q1 (M13-15)	Q2 (M16-18)	Q3 (M19-21)	Q4 (M22-24)	Q1 (M25-27)	Q2 (M28-30)	Q3 (M31-33)	Q4 (M34-36)	
WP 10: PILOTS	SCHNEIDER													
10.1 PILOTS METHODOLOGY PREPARATION	Schneider			★		★					★			
10.2 DATA COLLECTION AND MANAGEMENT	Schneider							★						
10.3 PILOT IN NORWAY	Lyse									★				★
10.4 PILOT IN THE NETHERLANDS	GreenFlux Elaad									★				★
10.5 PILOT IN BULGARIA	ALBENA									★				★
10.6 PILOT IN GERMANY	NewEn									★				★
10.7 PILOT IN SPAIN	EPESA									★				★
10.8 VALIDATION AND CERTIFICATION	Schneider										★			★

Figure 17: Work Package 10 planning

Overall progress at work package level

The progress in WP10 is according to the WP progress planning, except for the German pilot, T10.6. Due to piloting agreement hindrances, NewEn decided to leave the INVADE project. NewEn were replaced by another German pilot-partner, Badenova, approved by the EU-commission during June 2018. Badenova will be active from Q3 2018 and will catch up with the other pilots as soon as possible.

- T10.1. Pilots methodology preparation

Pilot Specification.

In T.10.1 we have described the general specifications/situation and provisions for each of the pilots in the INVADE Project. The pilots are located in four countries: Norway, Netherlands, Bulgaria and Spain. The fifth Pilot-site, in Germany, will be integrated in during Q3 2018, after approval by the EU-commission

We have described each pilot in chapters: A general definition, large scale proposal, technical characteristics, grid topology, technical details, storage details, flexibility services, use cases for each pilot, and a list of equipment to be installed in the pilots.

Pilot Methodology.

In T.10.1 we also have defined specific KPIs, pilot implementation process and objectives from a business point of view for each pilot in the project. We have been defining a list of KPIs, some are common for all the pilots, and others who are specific for each of them.

- T10.2 Data collection and management

In this task we have described the customer/participants recruiting processes, data collecting processes, data exchange processes and data deleting processes. It describes the data protection processes (Ethics/GDPR), and the “deleting”-process if participants want to leave the project. It also describes the data exchange processes between the pilots and the INVADE platform, the internal data processing inside the INVADE platform, and the data exchange processes between the INVADE platform and

sources for “external input” (Price, weather, Flexibility...) We have also deployed contract templates.

To identify needs and establish procedures for data-handling and contracts, pilot by pilot, we are using this common flowchart.

Figure 18: Data management flowchart applied in the pilots

Implementation details, for each pilot, is described in in the Deliverable D.10.3.

- T10.3 Pilot in Norway

The Norwegian pilot demonstrates how the INVADE platform will cooperate with an existing ecosystem to enable energy related services to end customers at private households and housing cooperatives. To enable this the pilot has many different setups of connected energy centric equipment to be controlled. The pilots in Stavanger is about the home and the end customer. Smart system of renewable energy storage based on smarthome platform with integrated EV's PV systems and batteries to empower mobile and decentralised energy storage in the distribution grid.

The sub pilot's setup:

- Case A: Heating control 3 zones + water heater control
- Case B: Smart EV charger
- Case C: 5 kWh battery energy storage

- Case D: 3 kWp solar plant + 5 kWh battery for energy storage
- Case E: 3 kWp solar plant + 5 kWh battery for energy storage + Smart EV charger
- Case F: 3 kWp solar plant, EV charger and water heater control
- Case G: Charging solutions in housing association
- Case H: 7 kWp solar plant + 10 kWh battery for energy storage + 11 Smart EV charger

The first 18 months of the project has been divide in two: 1. The technical implementation and 2. the pilot role out. For the technical part, a lot of effort has been to get all necessary API documentation from different suppliers and to integrate them to the existing ecosystem. Establishing a connection to the INVADE platform has also been a part of this work. The pilot role out has been done as a part of the existing business at Lyse + some new components. The role out of the pilots has been according to the progress plan, and most of the pilots have been installed.

- T10.4 Pilot in The Netherlands

During the first 18 month of the project the Dutch pilot (executed by Elaad and GreenFlux) was split in 4 individual sub-pilots to ensure that it was large scale and that the results would be replicable after the pilot. The four sub-pilots are:

- Home usage of EVs in combination with smart charging
- Office and parking lot usage of EVs in combination with smart charging and PV energy generation
- Office usage of energy and EVs with trials on Storage and V2G
- Public large-scale charge infra and with smart charging reducing the grid impact

To setup the pilot an improved protocol was designed that will be available for the public usage after the pilot if the results are as expected. This OSCP protocol should be part of the updated and existing OSCP protocol which is meant for communication with grid companies about available and needed amount of energy.

All 4 sub pilots have been setup and ready to start. Connection with the eSmart cloud system has been made and tested (using the OSCP protocol) and pilot users are informed. Also mobile app is developed so the end user can see his energy situation. At Elaad a huge test area was setup and opened to test several of the INVADE cases. First results from the Dutch pilot are expected the coming weeks.

- T10.5 Pilot in Bulgaria

The Bulgarian pilot demonstrates the benefits of a centralized energy storage combined with renewables and controllable loads. A centralised battery storage with capacity of 201 kWh, a 27kWp PV station and controllable loads were designed and connected to work together and to provide flexibility to a flexibility operator.

The first half of the project was mostly used for research and planning of the implementation. Accent was put on the possibilities for large scale extension. It was performed a deep analysis on the legislative and accounting ways to achieve a battery in Bulgaria, because the term “battery storage” is not used in any energy law or ordinance. It was also performed a deep study for the life cycle of the batteries which correlates with the load profile of the customer and, therefore, with the dimensioning of the equipment.

Now the process of supplying a battery is well documented and automated and is ready to be rolled up at the site of further stakeholders.

Parallel to the battery related works, a PV station was constructed on the rooftop of a five-star hotel. Except for generation of clean energy, the goal of the PV station is to bring additional volatility in the consumption of the customer. The energy consumption volatility is an obstacle for a wider use of PV by industrial customers, because it leads to imbalances in the energy consumption prediction, which leads to financial penalties. Therefore, the PV station is important part of the pilot site.

Within the first period of the project potential for controllable loads was identified. The boiler equipment for providing domestic hot water to the tourists is controlled by an industrial programmable logic controller. It reports the amount of stored energy in the boilers and which of the when can be switched on and off. This represents flexibility, which can be used for energy portfolio optimisation and serve as an additive to the battery operation. In order to reach more potential stakeholders, the boilers of two hotels are used – the first one is a newly build 5-star hotel, and the second one is an old 3-star hotel. Together, they represent the majority of hotels in Europe. During the preparation phase a lot of efforts were made, in order the model to be easily conveyed to further customers.

All activities within the project are planned to be communicated to more than 200,000 visitors in Albena annually.

- T10.6 Pilot in Germany

During the first 18 months of the project NewEn was responsible for the search and the operation of a demo site in Germany, to organize all necessary construction and conversion measures as well as communication between the participants on site and the project partners.

In the period from January to November 2017 the focus of the NewEn was on identifying a demo site according to the DoA specification and the application case number 4 (hybrid/ combination of centralized and distributed energy storage units). The focus for the pilot site is the integration of the INVADE platform into an existing grid infrastructure on the low and medium voltage level. According to the DoA, a central battery storage facility (up to 100 kWh) and several house battery storage facilities (up to 10 kWh) are planned for implementation in the German pilot.

The evaluation of the pilot sites examined came to the conclusion that the following points prevented NewEn participation in the INVADE project:

- For the INVADE hybrid/central battery storage use case, the municipal utilities were unable to identify any direct grid areas. All grid areas examined in the pilots were sufficiently dimensioned and there was no direct need for a central storage facility with 100 kWh or more. Compromise solutions would have been too costly
- Regulatory and legal obstacles. There is currently no clear legal situation with regard to the statutory fees and allocations for the feeding of electricity into battery storage. Electricity consumption in Germany is subject to various levies and charges. In case of storage there is Double burden fees of the electricity price (detailed information see Monthly report Aug 2017).

- Grid operator access approval for INVADE Flexibility Management Cloud central storage control. Problems of grid intervention by third parties! Failure of the central storage unit during network operation and thus feedback to the network. Liability for damages and insurance.
- Grid sections in the neighbourhoods that have a sufficient proportion of buildings with renewable energy production (PV system) and at the same time agree to the installation of a house storage could not be located in a coherent manner. The interested participants were spread over different network sections, so that a central storage unit could not be installed.
- Missing connection concepts for the central memory after completion of the INVADE project. All pilots would have had to be completely dismantled and decommissioned >> Loss of investment.
- Decisions take too much time at the municipal utilities (the board meets only every 3 months).
- NewEn is not a grid operator or municipal utility. All decisions for the control of the central energy storage unit were dependent on third parties. Especially the Flexibility Control Cloud from INVADE would have no direct access to the installations without separate agreements from the DSO.

Thus a new Partner (badenova) was invited to join the consortium in substitution of NewEn, starting the work late June, which objective is to build a German pilot as per the DoA description during the period 2.

- T10.7 Pilot in Catalonia

The Spanish pilot addresses use case 2, where a centralized battery is installed at a secondary substation and provides flexibility to the DSO and BRP.

During the first period of the project, the Spanish pilot has identified and validated the location and infrastructure used in the pilot as a large-scale concept. One primary substation will be used, along with twelve secondary substations and a critical building with the control center room of the DSO.

During this period an evaluation of storage devices was done, comparing between different suppliers and characteristics in order to choose the most appropriate device. The battery was chosen and purchased, and it is currently being assembled and integrated with the power electronics device.

To ensure the correct validation of the invade platform, an identification of which data to be used from the pilot area and the methods to access this data had to be done. It was identified that it would be necessary to install measurement devices at the secondary substations to have real-time data for the pilot evaluation. These installations took place during this first period of the project.

The evaluation and definition of the methodology to be used by the Invade platform users was carried out, where it was identified the software required to evaluate and correctly operate with the platform.

- T10.8 Validation and certification

This task is starting at M18, then no comment is added related to period 1.

Deviations and impact on the task planning

Due to the German pilot sites “late arrival” in INVADE, all deliverables in WP10 needs to be reopened and updated. It also impacts on increased T10.6 workload during period 2.

Proposed deviations’ corrective actions

Additional resources will be allocated to WP10 in order to scope with the German pilot challenge. This pilot-site aims to be executed and evaluated during only 18 months (period 2).

Role of partners

In WP10, all partners are involved, coordinated by the WPL, Schneider. All five pilot owners (Lyse, Estabanell, Albena, Greenflux/Elaad, and Badenova) are responsible for the “local” actions at their pilot sites, while the other partners strongly influence/contributes through their specific knowledge area.

1.2.11 Work package 11: Ethics

Overall objectives of the work package

Compliance with legal and ethical requirements relating to privacy and personal data preservation, which may also lead to consider the protection of other fundamental rights exercised in the private sphere is part of WP8 – Integrated INVADE platform, WP 9 Business Models and WP10 Pilots. The INVADE project implies collecting data from several Pilot communities members. During the pilots implementation INVADE will ensure that for engaged citizens the personal data processing complies with legal and ethical requirements. This is an integrated part of WP10 task T 10.2 and WP9 task T 9.2 as well as all implications considering pilot implementations in each site.

The Ethics Summary Report *Ref. Ares(2016)2871398 - 21/06/2016: Ethics Summary Report* identifies all the ethical issues and post grant requirements.

Ethics Issues identified are Human participation, and collection, storage and processing of research data:

- Humans
 - During the project, individual behaviour patterns will be analyzed, as well as the different types of instruments that impact the behavior of individuals. Gender aspects of habits in energy usage and management will be analysed (chapter 1.3.5, p.16)
- Protection of personal data (POPD)
 - Data acquired in the research work with human participants will be collected, retained and processed. However, the categories of personal data that will be collected in pilot studies are not explicitly specified. This is not clear whether sensitive data other than gender (chapter 1.3.5, p.16) or previously collected personal data shall be recorded
- Third countries
 - Personal data collected in pilots; Norway

Overall progress at work package level

Post Grant Requirements, Deliverables and Milestones

- D11.1 – Humans (M4)
 - 2.1. Details on the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants must be provided.
 - 2.2. Detailed information must be provided on the informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participation of humans.
 - 2.3. Templates of the informed consent forms and information sheet must be submitted.
 - 2.8. Details on incidental findings policy must be provided.
- D11.2 – POPD (M4)
 - 4.1. Copies of opinion or confirmation by the competent Institutional Data Protection Officer and/or authorization or notification by the National Data Protection Authority must be submitted (which ever applies according to the Data Protection Directive (EC Directive 95/46, currently under revision, and the national law).
 - 4.3. Justification must be given in case of collection and/or processing of personal sensitive data.
 - 4.4. Detailed information must be provided on the procedures that will be implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation.
- D11.3 - Non-EU country (M4)
 - 6.1. The applicant must confirm that the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon2020 will be rigorously applied, regardless of the country in which the research is carried out.
 - 6.3. The applicant must provide details on the material which will be imported to/exported from EU (explicit description of personal data that will be or are likely to be collected in pilots).

It includes Legal/regulatory issues in pilots' sites

1.3 Impact

The impacts that have been targeted in the proposal and that are maintained by the project still holds. As policies, technology maturity among people and policy makers improve and markets develop emphasis on each of the targeted impacts specified changes somewhat.

Developments in battery and storage technologies changes the way regulators, end-users and DSOs now think compared to a few years ago. The current changes in the certificate market creates new opportunities. New knowledge developed in the project and beyond creates new possibilities for self-consumption of locally generated energy. With the development of the Bulgarian pilot we expect to be able to demonstrate more on energy diversity. The new German pilot owner, Badenova, introduces new concerns that stresses the need for additional user incentives for investing in and maintaining

renewable sources, as historic and heavily subsidized end-user contracts terminates. This demands attention from the project.

Our proposal resolved here can serve as a model for many others. We lay the foundations for a whole new set of business models and technologies that can connect disparate enterprises and communities in diverse fields across Europe and leverage their ventures in the renewable, EV, energy or other energy demanding businesses. Especially related to EV roaming and e-mobility the concept developed might become very influential. This relates to our ambition for increased scalability of the takeaways that the project caters for.

DSOs will be offered suits of software, contractual templates and knowledge that will allow them to respond to quality and load issues in a quick and coherent manner. Local balance control will be possible.

These types of impacts are pivotal. We now see the possibilities of supporting the development of “green tourism” and “green living” too. We have already made our contribution to the finalization of the OCPP 2.0 protocol. We follow similar developments closely and adjust the course of our work accordingly. The project needs to be opportunistic as well as plan oriented in its attempt to create the impacts defined.

2. Update of the plan for exploitation and dissemination of result

The dissemination plan has been updated including a new section about non-scientific conferences and fairs planning. This section explains which events will be prioritized and scheduled from M18 until M36. The main events are the Smart City EXPO, InnoGrid2020+, Nordic Edge Expo and the European Utility Week. They are mainly scheduled for the third year when pilots are live, the INVADE integrated platform is working and they can show initial results and findings.

3. Update of the data management plan

The data management plan has been updated with more detailed information related to making the pilot data openly accessible. All pilots will publish electricity data to show the performance of their interaction with the INVADE integrated platform.

4. Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous review

n.a.

5. Deviations from Annex 1

5.1 Tasks

During the period 1, the only issue regarding tasks not fully implemented is related to the German pilot. The impossibility to built the pilot during the period has caused the shift of partner in that country, affecting the Gantt; the new DoA approved includes the new gantt that should allow to perform the German pilot withing the project duration.

This issue has caused also the request for re-submission of deliverables D4.2 INVADE architecture of pilots (submitted at M10) and D10.1 Pilots specifications (submitted at M8); these deliverables must include the german information that is impossible to obtain until the new partner badenova starts the work and built the pilot, providing all the necessary information to WP4 and WP10. Deliverables D4.2 and D10.1 will be submitted again as soon as badenova get its pilot designed and agreed with the corresponding municipalities and stakeholders.

5.2 Use of resources

Referred to the first period of the project, the use of resources was as follows:

- Personnel resources:

Reported M18	WP1		WP2		WP3		WP4		WP5		WP6		WP7		WP8		WP9		WP10		Total		Deviation		
	Actual	Plan	Actual	Plan	Actual	Plan																			
SmartIO	15.73	15.15	13.77	9.23	11.76	13.11	0.80	0.71	4.82	5.20	0.08	0.75					5.42	3.29	1.55	0.50	53.93	47.94	5.99	12.5%	
UPC	1.54	1.54	5.36	5.36	2.19	2.19	20.60	20.80	23.10	23.10					13.95	13.95	4.00	4.00	1.25	1.25	71.99	72.19	-0.20	-0.3%	
NTNU	2.00	1.63	0.58	1.51	0.99	1.80	0.19	0.80	39.96	37.00	0.15	2.40					1.68	6.29		0.92	45.55	52.35	-6.80	-13.0%	
VTT	0.87	0.92	0.50	0.83	0.81	0.86	0.33	0.33	1.00	1.34	29.70	33.36					0.05	0.28	0.30	0.58	33.56	36.49	-4.93	-12.8%	
eSmart	1.10	1.31	0.02	1.41	0.29	3.07	8.49	9.38	6.70	4.69			1.22	5.17	55.78	37.52	1.11	2.00	3.77	5.26	78.47	69.79	8.69	12.4%	
NewEn	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.70	0.70	0.50	0.50			0.30	0.30					0.20	0.20	3.10	3.10	5.00	5.00			
Albena	2.42	2.40	2.15	2.10	5.20	5.20	5.00	3.00			2.00	2.00	2.67	2.87	0.80		2.48	4.00	19.36	19.66	41.28	42.03	-0.75	-1.8%	
Schneider	0.80	1.30	0.25	1.60	0.85	3.60	4.40	6.50	2.20	2.90	0.70	2.20	14.57	20.30	1.25	2.75	0.70	1.60	5.20	10.30	30.92	53.05	-22.13	-41.7%	
SFR							0.10		0.10											0.90		3.00		-3.00	-100.0%
Lyse	0.96	1.41	0.35	0.90	0.75	4.92	1.58	3.00	0.68	3.10			2.76	2.00	0.16		7.88	11.20	24.67	14.60	39.79	41.13	-1.34	-3.3%	
Lyse Elnett																			1.01	6.50	1.01	6.50	-5.49	-84.5%	
EPESA	1.48	1.25	1.08	1.25	3.83	3.50	3.30	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.05	1.50	2.83	2.90	0.04	0.98	2.25	1.83	17.71	24.57	36.56	42.78	-6.23	-14.6%	
Elaad	2.40	1.65	0.28	1.00	6.26	6.12	8.19	7.00	6.01	6.00			3.21	4.00	2.25	2.50	6.47	7.91	16.45	10.98	51.52	47.16	4.36	9.2%	
GreenFlux	2.31	2.36	1.83	1.95	4.96	4.90	7.17	7.18	10.12	10.10			2.59	2.63	9.57	5.29	1.90	1.92	18.38	16.26	58.83	52.59	6.24	11.9%	
ICT															8.90	8.61			3.95	3.94	12.85	12.55	0.30	2.4%	
badenova	0.02	0.01																			0.02	0.01	0.01	100.0%	
WarmePlus																									
badenCampus																									
ITG																			0.01		0.01			0.01	
E-Maks																									
Netze																									
Total per WP	31.72	31.02	26.27	27.24	38.58	49.96	60.55	62.29	96.59	95.53	34.98	42.51	29.85	41.57	91.90	72.59	34.13	44.51	116.71	119.33	561.29	586.56	-25.27	-4.3%	
<i>Deviations</i>	0.70	-0.97	-11.38	-1.74	1.06	-7.53	-11.73	19.31	-10.38	-2.61	-25.27														
	2.3%	-3.6%	-22.8%	-2.8%	1.1%	-17.7%	-28.2%	26.6%	-23.3%	-2.2%	-4.3%														

Table 4 – Overall personnel resources reported/planned

- Other direct costs:

DoA	SmartIO	UPC	NTNU	VTT	eSmart	NewEn	Albena	Schneider	SFR	Lyse	Lyse Elnett	EPESA	Elaad	GreenFlux	badenova	TOTAL
Travel & Subsistence	57,600	40,500	55,000	40,500	40,500	35,100	35,100	69,300		31,600	3,500	35,100	35,100	35,100	24,000	538,000
Equipment		31,400			145,000	285,000	240,000	15,000		300,100		191,000	95,000	185,000	128,631.14	1,616,131.14
Other goods & services	83,800	49,600	16,600	25,200	15,000	11,000	11,000	9,000	5,000	11,000		34,400	8,000	8,000	5,000	292,600
Large Research Infrastructure				170,071												170,071
Subcontracting												120,000				120,000
TOTAL	141,400	121,500	71,600	235,771	200,500	331,100	286,100	93,300		342,700	3,500	380,500	138,100	228,100	157,631.14	2,731,802.14

Table 5 – Other directs costs as per the DoA

Reported at M18	SmartIO	UPC	NTNU	VTT	eSmart	NewEn	Albena	Schneider	SFR	Lyse	Lyse Elnett	EPESA	Elaad	GreenFlux	badenova	TOTAL
Travel & Subsistence	29,381.61	9,611.50	18,009.99	9,049.08	10,888.46	4,806.74	11,489.74	34,304.00		20,789.20	676.00	2,710.54	20,080.47	4,734.39		176,531.71
Equipment		6,015.39			52,026.71		1,704.81			244,405.50		78,654.18	171,969.91			554,776.50
Other goods & services	34,051.54	9,838.80		2,344.87	1,267.11		4,556.18						57,039.79			109,098.29
Large Research Infrastructure				81,925.50												81,925.50
Subcontracting												90,051.58				90,051.58
TOTAL	63,433.14	25,465.69	18,009.99	93,319.45	64,182.27	4,806.74	17,750.73	34,304.00		265,194.70	676.00	171,416.30	249,090.17	4,734.39		1,012,383.57

Table 6 – Other directs costs reported

Brief justification in case of resources deviations

The deviations in the personnel resources (both individually and for the consortium as a whole) are due to the non-linear distribution and use of the human resources along the project's duration. It is expected to increase the workload during the pilot and evaluation phases; Schneider, as WP leader for WP10 Pilots, is a good example of the expected increase of personnel resources to be used during period 2.

The shift of a partner and the inclusion of seven (7) new third parties has added and will represent additional workload to the project management (WP1), especially for the Grant and Consortium agreement and the different reporting (administrative and financial, internals and official progress reports).

Regarding the Other direct costs, no deviation has been encountered, less than 40% of the total amount has been used.

5.2.1 Unforeseen subcontracting

n.a.

5.2.2 Unforeseen use of in kind contribution from third party against payment or free of charges

n.a.